

ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF SULPHONES. PART I. CHELATION IN *o*-HYDROXYSULPHONES

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of 2-hydroxydiphenylsulphone, 4-hydroxydiphenylsulphone, 2-hydroxyphenyl-*p*-tolylsulphone and 4-hydroxyphenyl-*p*-tolylsulphone in ethanolic and cyclohexane solutions have been determined and compared with those of the corresponding methyl ethers. It is shown that chelation exists in 2-hydroxysulphones.

Morton and Stubbs (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1347), Burawoy and Chamberlain (*ibid.*, 1952, 2310, 3734) and Burawoy *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1955, 3727) have shown that an internal hydrogen bond displaces the B- and K-bands of phenols to longer wave-lengths. Thus, these bands in the spectra in hexane of 2-hydroxydiphenyl, 4-hydroxydiphenyl, 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 4-hydroxyazobenzene appear at shorter wave-lengths than in the spectra of the corresponding methyl ethers, whereas those of salicylaldehyde, 2-nitrophenol and 2-hydroxy-5-methylazobenzene are observed (in hexane) at longer wave-lengths than the corresponding bands of their methyl ethers. Another important criterion for the presence of an internal hydrogen bond is the characteristic effect of solvents (Burawoy *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The B- and K-bands of non-chelated phenols are displaced to longer wave-lengths as the dielectric constant of the solvent increases. This is due to the increased polarity of the absorbing system, resulting partly from the dielectric effect of the solvent and partly from the formation of an external hydrogen bond. On the other hand, the bands of chelated phenols are almost unchanged. In these phenols the existence of chelation inhibits the formation of an external hydrogen bond.

Though internal hydrogen-bond formation in compounds containing $-\text{NO}_2$, $>\text{CO}$ and $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ groups has been extensively studied; the same in sulphones has practically remained unexplored till recently. Amstutz *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 1220) studied the intramolecular hydrogen bond in certain *o*-substituted sulphones and sulfoxides by an examination of the spectra of these compounds in the infra-red region. They found chelation to occur in *o*-hydroxysulphones and sulfoxides, though the extent of interaction of the *o*-hydroxyl and sulphone groups was much less than that between *o*-hydroxyl and sulfoxide groups, as measured by the displacement of the fundamental absorption band of the OH group. The aim of the present investigation is to study the ultraviolet absorption spectra of some phenolic sulphones and to ascertain whether the electronic spectra data indicate the existence of hydrogen bonding in *o*-hydroxysulphones. The sulphones taken for the investigation were 2-hydroxydiphenyl-, 4-hydroxydiphenyl-, 2-hydroxyphenyl-*p*-tolyl-, 4-hydroxyphenyl-*p*-tolyl-sulphones and their methyl ethers. The spectra were taken both in cyclohexane and in ethanol. The data obtained are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Sulphone.	In cyclohexane.				In 25% ethanol.		
	Phenol.		Methyl ether.		Phenol.		Methyl ether.
	λ_{max} .	ϵ .	λ_{max} .	ϵ .	λ_{max} .	ϵ .	λ_{max} .
2-Hydroxydiphenyl-	295 m μ	4500	295 m μ	6600	295 m μ	4200	290 m μ 4600
	275	2500	285	6100	233	12600	235 12000
	238	10700	232	14600	220	16400	219 16400
			219	17100			
4-Hydroxydiphenyl-					205	4600	207 4600
	247	13000	252	18900	255	14100	254 13800
2-Hydroxyphenyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl	294	4900	285	4100	294	4400	290 4700
	244	14600	236	16000	238	15200	240 16100
			223	15900	225	14800	224 15500
4-Hydroxyphenyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	249	16500	253	20700	291	4200	
	225	9400	227	11000	256	16000	255 22000
			221	10700	223	12400	228 12000

Analysis of Spectra obtained in cycloHexane.—Considering the absorption spectra of the hydroxy compounds alone, the following observations may be made: The B-bands are seen in *o*-hydroxysulphones, while they are not seen in *p* hydroxysulphones. Presumably these bands are masked in *p*-hydroxysulphones. The appearance of the B-bands in *o*-hydroxysulphones can be explained on the basis of the formation of an internal hydrogen bond. Such a bond increases the polarity of the absorbing system in the ground state and this in turn can increase the intensity of the B-band, making it visible. Such a postulate may be expected to have other consequences, e.g. the increased polarity should displace the K-band also to a longer wave-length. This is seen not to be the case. In fact, the *p*-hydroxysulphone absorbs (K-band) at a longer wave-length. The explanation for this might be that the *p*-isomer has a longer conjugated system in the excited state.

It would be of interest to make such a comparison in the case of isomeric *o*- and *p*-hydroxy aldehydes, ketones, nitrobenzenes etc. But unfortunately comparable data, though available in alcohol solution, are not available in a non-polar solvent like hexane or cyclohexane (cf. Morton and Stubbs, *loc. cit.*, Burawoy and Chamberlain, *loc. cit.*, Burawoy *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). In these papers are recorded the ultraviolet absorption data in hexane solution for *o*-hydroxy compounds but not for *p*-hydroxy compounds, presumably due to the latter having a very low solubility in hexane. Even in the present investigation the *p*-hydroxysulphones were found to be only feebly soluble in cyclohexane. Solutions of the required concentration could, however, be obtained by dissolving a small amount of the substance in a large volume of the solvent.

Effect of Methylation on B- and K-bands in cycloHexane.—Methylation of a hydroxyl group *para* to the sulphonyl group has caused a slight shift of the B- and K-bands to longer wave-lengths with increase in intensity. This is the normal effect of methylation, in agreement with the greater electron-releasing power of the methyl group. On the other hand, methylation of a hydroxyl group in the *ortho* position resulted in a hypsochromic displacement of both the bands. These facts clearly establish the existence of chelation in *o*-hydroxysulphones,

Analysis of Spectra obtained in Ethanol.—Methylation displaces the B-bands of *o*-hydroxysulphones to shorter wave-lengths, the intensity being almost unaffected. The B-bands are not observed for the methyl ethers of *p*-hydroxysulphones, since they are masked by the more intense K-bands.

The effect of methylation on K-bands in ethanol is interesting. While in the case of *p*-hydroxysulphones methylation caused a hypsochromic shift, a bathochromic shift occurred for *o*-hydroxysulphones. This is just the reverse of what happens in cyclohexane. The observed shifts to shorter wave-lengths are due to a reversal of the bathochromic effect of hydrogen-bond formation with the solvent.

Effect of Solvent and Detection of Chelation.—The B- and K-bands of phenols in which no chelation occurs are known to shift to longer wave-lengths with increase in the dielectric constant of the solvent (Burawoy *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3723). The present investigation has also revealed that a change from cyclohexane to ethanol displaces the K-band of *p*-hydroxysulphones to longer wave-lengths (B-band not observed in cyclohexane). On the other hand, the B-bands of the *o*-hydroxysulphones are almost unaffected on changing the solvent from cyclohexane to ethanol. The K-bands are, however, displaced to shorter wave-lengths. This is significant in view of the fact that the K-bands of salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-5-methylazobenzene and 2-nitrophenol are almost unchanged by changing the solvent from hexane to ethanol (Burawoy *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3728). The explanation for this seems to be that the $-SO_2-$ group forms weaker chelate links than the $-CHO$, $-N=N-$, or $-NO_2$ group and that the chelation in *o*-hydroxysulphones becomes weak in polar solvents like ethanol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Spectra were determined using a Beckman ultraviolet spectrophotometer, model DU. The *o*- and *p*-hydroxysulphones, and their methyl ethers were prepared as described in an earlier paper (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 513). The ethanol (95%) used as solvent was purified by distillation after treatment with lead acetate and sodium hydroxide. The cyclohexane used was purified by passing through a column of silica gel several times; it boiled at 81°.

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